

Robust ViT-enhanced Detection of Sacrificial Anodes in Harsh Underwater Conditions

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Abstract—The structural assessment of submerged cathodic protection systems in Offshore Wind Turbines (OWTs) is crucial for ensuring longevity and operational efficiency. Traditional underwater inspections are expensive, inefficient, and expose human divers to hazardous conditions.

This article aims to enhance the perception capabilities of underwater vehicles by introducing the Contextual Anode Locator in Varying Underwater Scenarios (CALVUS), a learning-based solution designed for the robust and precise detection of sacrificial anodes in harsh subsea environments. CALVUS leverages the feature extraction capabilities of a depth estimation ViT-based backbone to detect anode structures under challenging underwater conditions such as heavy marine snow, variable illumination, biofouling and motion blur.

Evaluation on a dataset composed of images captured at the ATLANTIS Test Centre, CALVUS shows a performance of AP@50 of 97.9 %, an improvement of 19.9 % over state-of-the-art networks such as YOLO and RT-DETR. These results demonstrate the added value of using depth features during the detection operation, ultimately contributing to improved OWT operational efficiency and reduced maintenance costs.

Index Terms—Offshore Wind, Anode Detection, ViT-enhanced learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing interest in clean and renewable energies, the demand for Offshore Wind Turbines (OWTs) has increased [1]. The offshore environments offer harsh environmental conditions that hinder the lifespan of the structures due to the wear and corrosion of its foundations. One of the most used methods to maintain the foundations of the OWTs from corrosion are sacrificial anodes. These anodes corrode in place of the turbine’s foundation, thereby extending its lifespan [3].

Traditional Operations and Maintenance (O&M) methods in marine environments often rely on human divers and Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs). However, the inherent costs and risks associated with these conventional approaches have motivated the development of safer and more efficient autonomous solutions [14] [15] [16]. Consequently, there is a growing interest in advanced systems, such as machine learning and computer vision-based detection, for autonomous condition assessment, which needs robust perception capabilities. Regular inspection remains critical for ensuring the effective operation and timely replacement of these anodes.

Underwater environments present several obstacles for computer vision-based inspection. Turbidity, varying lighting conditions, and biofouling significantly degrade image quality, making it difficult to accurately identify and assess anode conditions [17]. These factors, combined with the inherent limitations of underwater imaging technologies, such as light attenuation and backscatter, demand robust computer vision algorithms. Recent state of the art sensors [4] mitigate some of the challenges faced in this scenarios, such as backscatter and light attenuation, thereby enabling the acquisition of high-fidelity data from real environments. This data allows vision-based algorithms to achieve superior feature extraction, which is crucial for effectively detecting anodes in challenging environments like the sea.

This article introduces the Contextual Anode Locator in Varying Underwater Scenarios (CALVUS), a model designed to achieve accurate and robust anode detection in challenging sub-sea conditions. It leverages the powerful feature extraction capabilities of a Visual Transformer (ViT) and incorporates a Real-Time DEtection TRansformer (RT-DETR) based head to generate precise bounding box predictions from the learned features. By leveraging the improved feature extraction capabilities of a model trained for depth estimation, this method aims to improve detection performance in real-world offshore scenarios, ultimately enhancing the detection of anodes under challenging conditions.

The main contributions of this article are:

- The development of a learning-based architecture incorporating depth-aware feature extraction to achieve robust sacrificial anode detection in challenging underwater scenarios;
- Experiments with real data collected at the ATLANTIS Test Center [1] validate the CALVUS detection model as it achieves 75% AP and 97.9% AP@50.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows: Section II provides a literature review; Section III introduces the CALVUS architecture and the methodology employed; Section IV presents all experimental results; Finally, Section V summarizes the work done and offers a critical review of

the results achieved.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section provides a critical overview of existing object detection methodologies and their applicability to the unique challenges of underwater environments, ultimately highlighting the research gap in detecting structural elements such as sacrificial anodes.

A. Generic models for 2D Detection

To understand the potential and drawbacks of applying current 2D Detection methodologies, this section outlines the key characteristics and limitations of the state of the art architectures, such as YOLO, RT-DETR, and Vision Transformers (ViTs).

J. Redmon *et al.* (2015) [10] introduced the YOLO network, which was later improved, with a significant shift in the weight version in YOLOv8 [8]; the current most recent version is YOLOv12 [9]. While this architecture is a popular choice for object detection and classification due to its computational efficiency and real-time processing capabilities, its applicability to accurately detecting anodes in challenging underwater environments faces several limitations. Although the speed of YOLO is advantageous for timely analysis in dynamic underwater scenarios, its reliance on a grid-based detection mechanism can hinder the detection of anodes obscured by biofouling or partially degraded by corrosion. Furthermore, the inherent variability in anode appearance caused by inconsistent lighting and turbidity underwater can negatively impact YOLO's generalization ability, potentially increasing false negatives and reducing overall detection accuracy.

RT-DETR, first introduced by Y. Zhao *et al.* (2024) [5] and later improved by W. Lv *et al.* (2024) [6], uses a transformer-based architecture to achieve improved object detection accuracy, particularly in complex scenes. This enhanced accuracy is beneficial for distinguishing anodes from surrounding underwater structures and mitigating the effects of visual clutter. Moreover, its attention mechanism allows for better contextual understanding, potentially aiding in the detection of partially obscured or degraded anodes. However, although the global context is beneficial, RT-DETR's ability to capture finer details, such as the subtle textures indicative of initial biofouling accumulation, can be a limitation. The presence of significant biofouling, which might obscure subtle visual features of the anode, could make it challenging for RT-DETR to accurately distinguish heavily encrusted anodes from the background or other similarly textured underwater elements. Consequently, the potential occlusion of subtle anode features by biofouling and the generalization difficulties under diverse underwater conditions could hinder RT-DETR's detection performance, potentially increasing the rate of missed detections and lowering the overall reliability of anode identification.

ViTs, inspired by the Transformer architecture introduced by Vaswani *et al.* (2017) [11] and pioneered for image recognition by Dosovitskiy *et al.* (2020) [12], offer a distinct

approach to feature extraction by processing images as sequences of patches. This enables ViTs to capture long-range dependencies and potentially learn very fine-grained visual details across the entire image. The ability of ViTs to capture these subtle visual features could be particularly beneficial for identifying early indicators of anode degradation. However, ViTs can be computationally intensive, demanding substantial processing resources, which could be a limiting factor in real-time underwater applications.

Li *et al.* (2022) [13] explored the potential of using pre-trained ViT models. Following this, several approaches have leveraged pre-trained ViT backbones to reduce training time, a notable example being Apple's ML-Depth Pro [7]. While ML-Depth Pro is designed for monocular depth estimation, its architecture employs pre-trained ViT encoders applied to patches extracted at multiple scales, aiming to learn scale-invariant representations by sharing the weights of the patch encoder across these scales [7]. The success of such transfer learning strategies in achieving complex visual understanding tasks like depth estimation highlights the potential of adapting pre-trained ViT features for other challenging domains, including the complexities of underwater vision.

B. Underwater 2D Detection

The existing literature on object detection applied to underwater scenarios is limited, predominantly focusing on marine life rather than underwater structures. Shijia Z. *et al.* (2022) [19] proposed an FPN-Attention module for YOLOv4, while Kun L. *et al.* (2023) [20] integrated a Transformer self-attention mechanism into the YOLOv5 encoder. YOLO-Fish, by A. A. Nuksit *et al.* (2022) [22], improved small object feature extraction and introduced large-scale datasets. However, all these studies target marine life. More recently, J. Chen *et al.* (2024) [21] added a feature fusion framework to a YOLO-based architecture, and H. Zhou *et al.* (2024) [23] modified the YOLOv8 backbone for enhanced feature extraction. Again, these efforts are solely for marine life detection, emphasizing the research gap in detecting underwater structures.

Notably, C. Fahy *et al.* (2024) [24] have recently investigated sacrificial anode detection on OWTs using an off-the-shelf YOLOv8 model. While this work represents a valuable contribution, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations. The datasets employed exhibit some constraints in terms of both size and diversity. Specifically, the offshore dataset was acquired from only two turbine bases, which may restrict the model's capacity for generalization to anodes situated in different contexts, potentially characterized by variations in biofouling, illumination, or structural morphology. Furthermore, the tank-based experiments, conducted to evaluate robustness, used 3D-printed anodes that present a notable discrepancy in visual appearance compared to real-world counterparts, potentially impacting the transferability of the findings to operational scenarios. These limitations in data representation emphasize the importance of developing more robust and generalizable methodologies for underwater anode detection.

Fig. 1: Proposed system architecture. Input images are pre-processed to 1536x1536 and applied a CLAHE algorithm, followed by feature extraction using the ML-Depth Pro patch encoder backbone. The resulting feature APs are then processed by an RT-DETR-style head for object classification and bounding box regression.

C. Final Considerations

In conclusion, this review of the literature underscores a significant research gap in the application of advanced object detection techniques to underwater structural elements. While models like YOLO [10] [8] [9] and RT-DETR [5] [6] have achieved considerable success in various domains, their direct use in detecting complex and variable underwater structures like anodes is limited and potentially suboptimal. The existing body of work predominantly focuses on marine life, leaving a critical need for dedicated research into methods capable of handling the unique visual challenges of subsea environments. This review highlights the critical need for further investigation into tailored approaches that can overcome issues such as occlusion, degradation, and inconsistent visual features to enable robust and reliable detection of underwater structures such as sacrificial anodes.

III. CALVUS A ViT-BASED NETWORK FOR ANODE DETECTION

This section introduces CALVUS, a ViT-based network designed for robust underwater anode detection by leveraging pre-trained ViT architectures. To significantly reduce the extensive training time typically associated with such deep networks, CALVUS repurposes a pre-trained ViT backbone, specifically the one used in the ML-Depth Pro network [7]. While originally designed for depth estimation, we hypothesize that the inherent capacity of depth-aware networks to discern fine-grained spatial information and subtle visual distinctions will yield superior feature representations crucial for accurate anode identification in challenging subsea conditions, all while avoiding lengthy training from scratch.

For feature extraction, CALVUS adapts the patch encoder structure of the ML-Depth Pro network [7]. As depicted in Figure 1, the input image of 1536x1536 is first processed into three scaled versions: 1536x1536, 768x768, and 384x384. Since the patch encoder in this ViT architecture operates on 384x384 patches, the two larger scaled images are divided into overlapping patches of this size. All extracted patches are then

concatenated and fed into the patch encoder. Subsequently, the encoder’s output features are split back into three feature APs corresponding to the input scales: 96x96x1024 (from 1536x1536), 48x48x1024 (from 768x768), and 24x24x1024 (from 384x384) [7].

Subsequently, these multi-scale feature APs are processed through a RT-DETR head, with a modified input head tailored to the output dimensions of the repurposed patch encoder with 1024 features instead of the usual 256, to generate anode bounding boxes and class confidence scores.

To improve the quality of the images and to mitigate color distortion caused by the sub-sea environment, CALVUS has a pre-processing phase that applies a Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) algorithm [18]. CLAHE enhances local contrast by dividing the image into small tiles, applying histogram equalization to each tile independently, and then combining the results using bilinear interpolation to eliminate artificially induced boundaries. This adaptive approach helps to reveal finer details, correct for uneven illumination and fix color distortion, which is crucial in the challenging underwater imaging conditions. This pre-processing, combined with the MARESyE image acquisition techniques [2], provided the model with an input with much sharper details and less noise which lead to an improvement in the overall performance. The full system’s structure can be seen in Figure 1.

To enhance the model’s robustness against the diverse challenges posed by harsh underwater conditions, several augmentation techniques were implemented, visually exemplified in Figure 2:

- **Motion Blur:** Simulated the image blurring resulting from capture on a moving platform (Figure 2b).
- **Salt and Pepper Noise:** Introduced noise to replicate the effect of marine snow in the water (Figure 2c).
- **RGB Channel Shift:** Altered the green and blue channels to emulate the characteristic color shift observed in deeper sea environments (Figure 2d).
- **Illumination Variation:** Modified image illumination

Fig. 2: Original image and augmented versions demonstrating the techniques used to simulate the harsh and challenging conditions encountered in sub-sea environments.

to simulate both the diminished light levels at greater depths and the increased illumination closer to the surface (Figure 2e).

In addition to these augmentations, horizontal and vertical flips were also used, as well as random rotations, to improve the model’s generalization capabilities.

CALVUS was trained by initializing the model with pre-trained weights for the patch encoder backbone and the RT-DETR head. Subsequently, the backbone’s weights were frozen to maintain its learned feature extraction capabilities, focusing solely on retraining the RT-DETR head. This approach ensured that the head adapted to the new feature APs generated by the pre-trained backbone, enabling accurate anode classification.

For performance evaluation during both the training and validation phases, the official RT-DETR loss function was used, specifically the RTDETRLoss. This loss function comprises three main components: classification loss, bounding box regression with GIoU, and a denoising element. The denoising part of the loss intentionally introduces noise during training, aiming to enhance the model’s robustness and ensure accurate detection even in the presence of noisy inputs, which is particularly relevant in underwater where images are constantly being contaminated with noise. By combining these three elements, this loss provides a comprehensive understanding of the model’s performance and its ability to generalize.

The training strategy used the AdamW optimizer and a ReduceLRonPlateau scheduler to manage learning rate decay. Batches of 6 samples were used for training over a maximum of 50 epochs, with early stopping over the validation loss employed as a regularization technique. All computations were carried out on an RTX 2080 SUPER GPU with 8GB of VRAM.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To ensure a fair comparison between the proposed model and state-of-the-art methods, YOLO and RT-DETR were both trained using an identical transfer learning strategy. Specifically, the backbones of these models was frozen and retrained only their detection heads and the pre-processing pipeline used the same augmentations. This approach allowed to effectively evaluate the differences in feature extraction capabilities between the established architectures and CALVUS’s backbone.

The architectures of RT-DETR and YOLO are designed for an input image size of 640x640 while CALVUS leverages a larger 1536x1536 input. This architectural divergence implies that CALVUS is structured to process more information, potentially enhancing its capacity of feature extraction at the cost of increased computational resources.

All models were trained and tested on a dataset with one anode per image captured by MARESyE [2] and FIFISH¹ in a real-world scenario in Viana do Castelo, and background images were sourced from the NEREON dataset [25]. The final dataset consisted of 19189 training images, 3417 validation images, and 4540 test images.

The performance metrics resulting from this evaluation are presented in Table I. The models were compared based on the following metrics:

- **AP:** Average Precision averaged across IoU thresholds from 0.50 to 0.95 with a step interval of 0.05;
- **AP@50 and AP@75:** Average Precision for IoU thresholds of 0.50 and 0.75, respectively;
- **IoU@50:** average Intersection over Union of detections with a minimum IoU of 0.5.

¹<https://store.qysea.com/fifish-v6.html>

Fig. 3: Comparison of CALVUS and YOLO11x detections in varying scenarios.

TABLE I: Performance results of the proposed CALVUS model compared to baseline object detection architectures (YOLO and RT-DETR-L) on the real-world dataset.

Model	Size	AP	AP@50	AP@75	IoU@50
YOLO11x	640	0.624	0.780	0.697	0.886
YOLO12x	640	0.573	0.711	0.640	0.891
RT-DETR-L	640	0.345	0.435	0.398	0.887
CALVUS	1536	0.750	0.979	0.883	0.893

The quantitative results presented in Table I demonstrate the superior performance of our proposed model across all evaluated metrics compared to RT-DETR-L and the various YOLO versions tested. When applied directly to our target problem without specific retraining, the RT-DETR-L backbone exhibits a limited ability to effectively capture relevant features across diverse underwater environments, resulting in comparatively underwhelming AP values, achieving only 0.345 and 0.435 for AP and AP@50, respectively. Conversely, the YOLO models show similar performance across versions, with YOLO11x achieving marginally better results with an AP of 0.623 and an AP@50 of 0.778. While the YOLO backbone yields better results compared to RT-DETR-L, it still falls short of our model’s performance, with CALVUS achieving an AP of 0.750 and an AP@50 of 0.979. This performance strongly validates our hypothesis that CALVUS exhibits better feature extraction capabilities compared to the current state of the art used in object detection.

Figure 3 presents a comparative illustration of object detection outputs from CALVUS and YOLO11x across four distinct instances. As depicted in Figure 3, Instance 1 demonstrates a scenario with motion blur, a condition that CALVUS was specifically trained to address through data augmentation. In this instance, CALVUS accurately predicts the object with a single bounding box, showcasing its robustness to motion blur,

(a) YOLOx11

(b) CALVUS

Fig. 4: Confusion matrices highlighting classification results on the test dataset for YOLO11x and CALVUS.

while YOLO11x generates two bounding boxes for the same object. Instances 2 and 3 highlight the models’ performance in the presence of marine snow. In Instance 2, CALVUS correctly identifies the object with a single bounding box, whereas YOLO11x produces two bounding boxes. Under the more challenging conditions presented in Instance 3, CALVUS successfully detects the object, while YOLO11x fails to make any prediction. Finally, Instance 4 provides a compelling example of the benefits of using a backbone trained for depth information. Due to significant biofouling, the texture across the entire image exhibits high similarity, causing YOLO11x to incorrectly predict multiple anodes. In contrast, CALVUS, by extracting depth-related features, can effectively differentiate between the background and the single anode present, leading to a correct prediction.

Beyond the overall performance metrics, a qualitative analysis of the classification results can be obtained through the confusion matrices presented in Figure 4 for YOLO11x (the best-performing baseline identified in Table I) and CALVUS.

These matrices provide a detailed breakdown of the classification results, showing the counts of True Positives (correctly identified anodes), False Negatives (anodes that were missed), and False Positives (non-anodes that were incorrectly classified as anodes).

As depicted in Figure 4, CALVUS (b) demonstrates superior classification performance compared to the YOLO11x(a). Notably, the confusion matrix for YOLO11x reveals a significant issue with False Negatives, as 21.4% of actual anodes were incorrectly dismissed as background. In contrast, CALVUS shows a much lower False Negative rate of 1.3%. Furthermore, YOLO11x also exhibits a high rate of False Positives, with 4.1% of background samples being incorrectly classified as anodes, while CALVUS shows a False Positive rate of only 0.9%. This visual representation, highlighting the substantially lower False Negative rates of CALVUS and the significantly lower False Positive rates compared to YOLO11x, reinforces the quantitative findings presented in Table I, further substantiating the enhanced accuracy and robustness of the CALVUS architecture for underwater anode detection.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces CALVUS, a novel solution for the critical task of underwater anode detection, essential for OWT maintenance. By leveraging a pre-trained ViT backbone with an RT-DETR based head, the approach effectively addresses the challenges of object detection in complex subsea environments.

CALVUS demonstrates superior performance on a real-world dataset, achieving 75.0% AP and 97.9% AP@50, a significant improvement over YOLO (62.4% AP, 78.0% AP@50) and RT-DETR (34.5% AP, 43.5% AP@50). This enhanced accuracy and robustness positions CALVUS as a promising advancement for autonomous underwater inspection systems, offering a more reliable means of monitoring sacrificial anodes. Future research could explore integrating temporal information and assessing the model's generalization across more diverse datasets.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. M. Pinto et al., "ATLANTIS - The Atlantic Testing Platform for Maritime Robotics," OCEANS 2021: San Diego – Porto, San Diego, CA, USA, 2021, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.23919/OCEANS44145.2021.9706059.
- [2] Pedro Nuno Leite, Andry Maykol Pinto, "Fusing heterogeneous tri-dimensional information for reconstructing submerged structures in harsh sub-sea environments," *Information Fusion*, Volume 103, 2024, 102126, ISSN 1566-2535, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2023.102126>.
- [3] Abdel Salam H. Makhoul, Victor Herrera, Edgar Muñoz, "Chapter 6 - Corrosion and protection of the metallic structures in the petroleum industry due to corrosion and the techniques for protection," Editor(s): Abdel Salam Hamdy Makhoul, Mahmood Aliofkhaezai, *Handbook of Materials Failure Analysis*, Butterworth-Heinemann, 2018, Pages 107-122, ISBN 9780081019283, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-101928-3.00006-9>.
- [4] Andry Maykol Pinto, Anibal C. Matos, "MARESyE: A hybrid imaging system for underwater robotic applications," *Information Fusion*, Volume 55, 2020, Pages 16-29, ISSN 1566-2535, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2019.07.014>.
- [5] Y. Zhao et al., "DETRs Beat YOLOs on Real-time Object Detection," arXiv preprint arXiv:2304.08069, 2024.
- [6] W. Lv et al., "RT-DETRv2: Improved Baseline with Bag-of-Freebies for Real-Time Detection Transformer," arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.17140, 2024.
- [7] A. Bochkovskii, A. Delaunoy, H. Germain, M. Santos, Y. Zhou, S. R. Richter, and V. Koltun, "Depth Pro: Sharp Monocular Metric Depth in Less Than a Second," arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.02073, 2024.
- [8] R. Varghese and S. M., "YOLOv8: A Novel Object Detection Algorithm with Enhanced Performance and Robustness," 2024 International Conference on Advances in Data Engineering and Intelligent Computing Systems (ADICS), Chennai, India, 2024, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ADICS58448.2024.10533619.
- [9] Y. Tian, Q. Ye, and D. Doermann, "YOLOv12: Attention-Centric Real-Time Object Detectors," arXiv preprint arXiv:2502.12524, 2025.
- [10] J. Redmon et al., "You Only Look Once: Unified, Real-Time Object Detection," arXiv preprint arXiv:1506.02640, 2016.
- [11] A. Vaswani et al., "Attention is all you need," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 30, 2017.
- [12] A. Dosovitskiy et al., "An image is worth 16x16 words: Transformers for image recognition at scale," arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.11929, 2020.
- [13] Y. Li et al., "Exploring plain vision transformer backbones for object detection," in *European conference on computer vision*, pp. 280-296, Springer, 2022.
- [14] R. M. Claro et al., "Artuga: A novel multimodal fiducial marker for aerial robotics," *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 163, p. 104398, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.robot.2023.104398.
- [15] D. F. Campos et al., "Nautilus: An autonomous surface vehicle with a multilayer software architecture for offshore inspection," *Journal of Field Robotics*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 966-990, 2024, doi: 10.1002/rob.22304.
- [16] M.I. Pereira and A.M. Pinto, "Reinforcement learning based robot navigation using illegal actions for autonomous docking of surface vehicles in unknown environments," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 133, p. 108506, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.engappai.2024.108506.
- [17] P. N. Leite, P. N. Pereira, J. M. M. Dionísio, and A. M. Pinto, "Hybrid underwater imaging for the tri-dimensional inspection of critical structural elements in offshore platforms," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 314, p. 119658, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2024.119658>.
- [18] S. M. Pizer, R. E. Johnston, J. P. Erickson, B. C. Yankaskas, and K. E. Muller, "Contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization: speed and effectiveness," in [1990] *Proceedings of the First Conference on Visualization in Biomedical Computing*, pp. 337-345, 1990, doi: 10.1109/VBC.1990.109340.
- [19] S. Zhao, J. Zheng, S. Sun, and L. Zhang, "An Improved YOLO Algorithm for Fast and Accurate Underwater Object Detection," *Symmetry*, vol. 14, no. 8, p. 1669, 2022, doi: 10.3390/sym14081669.
- [20] K. Liu, L. Peng, and S. Tang, "Underwater Object Detection Using TC-YOLO with Attention Mechanisms," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 5, p. 2567, 2023, doi: 10.3390/s23052567.
- [21] J. Chen and M. J. Er, "Dynamic YOLO for small underwater object detection," *Artif Intell Rev*, vol. 57, p. 165, 2024, doi: 10.1007/s10462-024-10788-1.
- [22] A. A. Muksit et al., "YOLO-Fish: A robust fish detection model to detect fish in realistic underwater environment," *Ecological Informatics*, vol. 72, p. 101847, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2022.101847>.
- [23] H. Zhou et al., "Real-time underwater object detection technology for complex underwater environments based on deep learning," *Ecological Informatics*, vol. 82, p. 102680, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2024.102680>.
- [24] C. Fahy et al., "Automated Detection of Sacrificial Anodes on Offshore Wind Farms for ROV Inspections," OCEANS 2024 - Halifax, Halifax, NS, Canada, pp. 1-6, 2024, doi: 10.1109/OCEANS55160.2024.10753752.
- [25] J. M. M. Dionísio, P. N. A. S. Pereira, P. N. Leite, F. S. Neves, J. M. R. S. Tavares, and A. M. Pinto, "NEREON - An Underwater Dataset for Monocular Depth Estimation," OCEANS 2023 - Limerick, Limerick, Ireland, pp. 1-7, 2023, doi: 10.1109/OCEANSLimerick52467.2023.10244675.